

Evaluating the Impact of Peer Influence on Student Behaviour and Academic Performance in A Boarding School: A Case Study of a Private School in the Northern Region of Botswana

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the impact of peer influence on students' behaviour and academic performance. The respondents of the study comprised of 11 students from a private school located in the northern region of Botswana. Random interviews were conducted and the responses were recorded and analysed qualitatively using the Thematic Analysis model. Findings of the study revealed that boarding schools have two main peer groups, which consist of female peer groups, and male peer groups; whose dominance is demonstrated through aggressiveness, coercion and outright force. Findings also indicated that peer group influence has a negative and positive effect in modelling the behaviour of students more especially in a boarding school environment. Moreover, findings also showed that there is a significant relationship between peer influence and academic performance; the type of peer group affiliations one maintains influences this.

Keywords: Peer Influence & Affiliation; Student Behaviour; Academic Performance; Boarding School; Teenagers.

Introduction

Peer influence in schools has been around for as long as anyone can remember: various studies indicate that peer groups are formed in order to provide support, information and guidance to one another (Stumpers, Breen, Pooley & Pike, 2005). In boarding schools, peers spend a significant amount of time together, socializing and learning from each other (Poynting & Donaldson, 2005); these interactions provide opportunities for peer pressure to take place. Mugove (2017) asserted that when adolescents are left in boarding schools, it is the hope of parents that the school authorities take over the roles of parents as 'loco-parentis' to ensure that all peer interactions are done in the spirit of collegiality. Carlisle and Rofes (2007) further added that it is because when adolescents transition to a new environment, they experience another level of complexity in their lives, where they have to adapt to a temporary while building new relationships with their peers in the boarding school.

Understating peer influence

Teenagers more especially students, tend to associate with peers who share similar behaviors, preferences and attitudes including academic aspiration, music taste, political opinion, fashion style or preferred leisure activities (Brechtwald & Prinstein, 2011). Peer pressure refers to the influence exerted by a peer group in encouraging a person to change his/her attitudes and values in order to conform to group norms (Kirk, 2000). Ryan (2000) described peer pressure as a situation where people of one's own age encourage or urge the person to do something or to keep from doing something with less of their consent. According to Burns and Darling (2002), the more subtle form of peer pressure is known as peer influence as it involves changing one's behaviour to meet the perceived expectations of others. Other studies argued that participating in peer group activities is a primary stage of development because adolescents' identities are often closely associated with that of their peers (Santor, Deanne, & Kusumskur, 2000).

Studies by Ryan (2000) affirmed that for adolescents, other interests might compete with or take precedence over similar academic motives and engagements as a criterion for selecting a peer group; this could put an adolescent's motives and engagements towards school in a precarious position. Studies reveal that through selection, some adolescents may place themselves in peer group situations that support or foster their achievement-related beliefs and behaviour, while others may place themselves in contexts that weaken their academic achievement related beliefs and behaviour (Ryan, 2000; Landau, 2002).

Contrary to popular beliefs held by different peer groups that exit in boarding schools, spending time with peers does not always translate into trouble (Kirk, 2000). These findings also revealed that negative peer pressure has less effect on students' academic performance because students may mask their academic

achievement from their friends. Nevertheless, Ryan (2000) also argued that peer groups could be a source of affection, sympathy, understanding and a place for experimentation.

Thus, the primary aim of this study was to evaluate the extent to which peer pressure influences the behaviour and academic performance amongst boarding students at a private school located in the northern region of Botswana.

Background to the study

Literature on peer effects in education dates back to 1960s with the publication of the famous Coleman Report (1966), but the importance of peer-group effects is still disputed. Some very bold claims have been made about the potency of peers in child development (Rich, 1999), yet the Findings of numerous studies are very mixed, finding strong, weak or non-existent effects across a wide range of outcomes. The estimation of peer influences at school has received intense attention in recent years (Moffit, 2001). Recent examples include Angrist and Lang (2004) on peer influences through racial integration; Hoxby (2000) ; Lavy & Schlosser (2007) on gender peer influences; and Gould, Lavy & Paserman (2009) on the effect of immigrants on native students.

Students exist within dynamic environments such as homes, schools, churches and within communities of different cultures (Swearer, 2011). Teenagers usually form groups in school, which are amongst the most influential social forces that affect their behaviour; from mundane decisions concerning clothing, hairstyle, music and entertainment to more significant decisions concerning short and long-term educational plans (Mapesa, 2013).

Research reveals that adolescents are influenced by what their peers do and this also determines the type of peer groups that they affiliate with; these affiliations are principled around similar interests (Sarita, 2015). A study by Olalekan (2016) observed that peer groups which students belonged to influence their learning because they are faced with the urge to belong and to be accepted by members. Other, studies indicated that students in the midst of their group usually reveal their true behaviour, since they feel more comfortable in the presence of their peers (Olalekan, 2016). Furthermore, Olalekan (2016) affirmed that the most important influence on student behaviour to learning is not always about the teacher but sometimes it is all about peer students. Another similar study by Taiwo (2004) affirms that within the peer group dynamics, each child strives to abide with the ethics of the group that they take membership with.

In the context of Botswana, the impact of peer influence on academic performance and behaviour outcomes in private boarding schools is an area that has not received much intense investigation, thus, there is little literature available. Therefore, there was need to investigate on the peer influence on the behaviour and academic performance of students in a private boarding school.

Statement of the problem

Many factors contribute to student-behaviour outcomes and academic achievement either directly or indirectly, more especially at secondary boarding schools. Therefore, there is need to look into peer group relationships and individual approaches to learning, membership of peer group affiliations in order to find out how factors such as behaviour, age, social status and ethnicity determine peer group compositions and existence in boarding school environments.

Understanding the nature and the magnitude of peer group influence in education is crucial for this study as well as the organisational design of school systems. Peer group influences are a distinct class of influences arising from social interactions, which encompasses different types of behaviours that involve interdependency with the behaviour or characteristics of others.

The estimation of peer influence in school on a continental perspective has received intense attention in recent years and literature reflects the difficulty it has in defining the peer group, isolating causal peer group effects from other influences (Hoxby, 2000; Moffit, 2001; Lavy & Schlosser, 2007). Therefore, given the nature of peer group influences that have been observed in Botswana boarding schools, this study sought to evaluate the extent to which peer influence impact on the behaviour and academic achievement amongst students in the context of a private boarding school.

Purpose of the study

This study was conducted in order to establish how peer groups influence the behaviour and academic performance of students in a private boarding secondary school located in the northern region of Botswana in order to determine workable solutions towards addressing challenges that are experienced by schools in Botswana.

Objectives of the study

The study was guided by the following objectives:

- To establish types of predominant peer groups existent in private boarding schools.
- To examine how peer group relationships affect the behaviour of boarders.
- To evaluate how peer group composition influence academic performance.

Research questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- Which types of peer groups are predominant in private boarding schools?
- How does a peer group relationship affect the behaviour of boarders?
- How does peer group influence academic performance?

Significance of the study

These findings would be of great importance in establishing factors associated to peer group in relation to behaviour outcome and academic performance. This would also help develop and provide solutions to challenges faced by students and teachers regarding peer influence outcomes. Furthermore, these findings would provide some background information for future research on the topic area.

Theoretical framework

The Social Learning Theory

This study used the Social Learning Theory designed by Bandura (1977) which emphasizes the importance of observing and modelling the behaviours, attitudes, and emotional reactions of others. This theory is based on the major premise that behaviour is learned and can be unlearned. Bandura (1977) stated that learning would be exceedingly lengthy if people had to rely solely on the effects of their own actions to inform them on what to do. The Social Learning Theory Conditions for effective modelling include:

- Attention — this aspect holds that various factors increase or decrease the amount of attention paid by an individual. This includes distinctiveness, affective valence, prevalence, complexity and functional value (Bandura, 1977).
- Retention — this aspect speaks of an individual remembering what they paid attention to which includes symbolic coding, mental images, cognitive organization, symbolic rehearsal and motor rehearsal (Bandura, 1977).
- Reproduction — this aspect speaks of reproducing the image. Including physical capabilities, and self-observation of reproduction (Bandura, 1977).
- Motivation — this aspect speaks of having a good reason to imitate and this includes motives such as past (i.e. traditional behaviourism) promised (imagined incentives) and vicarious (seeing and recalling the reinforced model) (Bandura, 1977).
- Identification – this aspect speaks of taking on observed behaviours, values, beliefs and attitudes (Bandura, 1977).
- Modelling – this aspect speaks of individual changes in cognition, behaviour or effects that result from observation of others (Ryan, 2000).

The Social Learning Theory has been used to address a number of real-world applications. For example, studies have used the theory to investigate on how aggression and violence might be transmitted through observational learning (Bandura, 1977). The Social Learning Theory posits that man is born with some innate potential, which the environment conditions, that is, as adolescents interact in the environment; they consciously or unconsciously observe, imitate and display behaviour of models (Bandura, 1977). This

affirms that there is interrelationship between one's personality, behaviour and environmental factors. Ryan (2000) affirmed that observing others perform a particular behaviour or voice a certain opinion can introduce an individual to new behaviours and viewpoints that may be different from his or her own. Furthermore, Korir and Kipkemboi (2014) pointed out that observation enlightens an individual on the consequences of such behaviour and opinions. Thus, depending on the consequences, observation of a model can strengthen or weaken the likelihood that the observer will engage in such behaviour or adopt such beliefs.

Classification of role models

There are two types of role models, namely positive and negative role models. Lockwood and Kunda (2002) defined positive role models as individuals who has achieved outstanding success and are widely expected to influence others to pursue similar excellence. On the other hand, negative role models are those individuals who experienced misfortunes and are widely expected to motivate people to take the steps necessary to avoid similar unpleasant outcomes (Lockwood & Kunda, 2002).

Positive role models can inspire one by illustrating an ideal, desired self-highlighting possible achievement that one can strive for, and the root for achieving them. In a boarding school setting, peer groups play a key part in an individual's development process therefore; they have both the positive and negative effects on students due to peer pressure.

For this study, this theory was used to evaluate the impact of peer influence on student behaviour and academic performance in the context of private boarding schools. The theory could be an explanation for the seeming relationship that may exist amongst peer pressure, behaviour and academic performance.

Literature review

This study reviewed literature based on the research questions, which were premised on the following themes: Types of predominant peer groups' existent in private boarding schools: Peer group relationships and impact on the behaviour of boarders: Peer group composition and influence on academic performance.

Concept of Peer group

Castrogiovanni (2000) defined peer group as a small group of similar age and fairly close friends sharing the same activities. Studies discovered that a peer labelling process might be contributing to the construction of positive identities and negative identities amongst members (Ryan, 2000; Castrogiovanni, 2002; Downs & Rose, 1991). This is consistent with what Black (2002) asserted that peer groups provide a forum where teens construct and reconstruct their identities.

On the other hand, Ryan (2000) discovered that peer groups are commonly influential where there are intrinsic values for school as well as academic achievement. Furthermore, Ryan (2000) found out that associating with friends who have positive attitudes towards school, enhanced students' own satisfaction with school, whereas associating with friends who have negative attitudes towards school decreased the levels of motivation towards schoolwork. Findings by Landau (2002) highlighted that an adolescent's expectancy of success was the primary predictor of academic effort and grades; thus, a sense of belonging and support of a peer group is significantly associated with these outcomes.

Santor, Deanne, Kusumskur (2000) in their study discovered that teenagers learn about what is acceptable in their social group by reading their friends reactions to how they act, what they wear and how they behave in different situations. A similar study by Burns et al. (2000) affirmed that peer groups give potent feedback by their words and actions, which either encourages or discourages certain behaviour and attitudes. In addition, Burns et al. (2000) stated that self-conscious teenagers worry about how others react to their actions; these are some of the most common ways of how teenagers are influenced by their peers.

Types of predominant peer groups existent in private boarding schools

Boarding schools just like any other communities are principled by cultures, beliefs, norms and different types of behaviours that exist amongst learners as they build their peer relationships. Brown (2004) discovered that these predominant peer groups are based on joint identification of similar attitudes, shared values of lifestyles as well as ethnicity. Other studies identified several affiliations such as - academically focused peer groups (brains), high status peer groups (populars), deviant or antisocial peer groups (burnouts)

and adolescents without many peer affiliations (loners) as some of the types or peer groups that are found in boarding schools (Prinstein & La Greca, 2002; Rubin et al, 2007).

As pointed out by the reviewed literature, there are two main types of peer groups, which are mostly gender oriented. And these include:

- **Male Peer Groups**

Research shows that the existence of male peer groups that evolve in boarding schools under selective pressures that seek to take dominance and control over one's local environment are based on the available resources, friendships and affiliations (Geary, 2008). As such, boys in boarding schools often organise themselves into male coalitions which are properly organised according to highly dominant structures (Geary, 2010). From a cultural perspective, the emphasis on boys to demonstrate their levels of independence, self-sufficiency, and competitiveness may aggravate the tendency for boys to naturally organise themselves in peer groups that share the same values and norms (Benenson et al. 2001).

From an adaptive standpoint, especially in boarding schools, by developing associations amongst each other that are built on status and dominance, boys are able to compete against other groups of boys in a quest to protect their resources and territory (Geary, 1998). Within these male peer groups, one-on-one, group-level affiliations and competitiveness are influenced by acceptance, integrity and values for sentimental friendships.

- **Female Peer Groups**

Studies also revealed that girls in boarding schools tend to organize themselves into peer groups that consist of individuals who share the same sentiments and social status which are mostly characterised by personal disclosure, and support for one another (Waal, 1989).

Studies indicated that females are inclined to invest more profoundly in the quality of their relationships than in the quantity of relationships that they have (Benenson & Christakos, 2003). Research also showed that females engage in these kinds of peer groups for adaptiveness and a sense of belonging. For females, peer formation is influenced by significant benefits in having a network of reciprocating friendships (Geary, 2010).

While the intimate nature of female peer groups is beneficial, these similar qualities may also contribute to the rejection of such afflictions when individual needs are not met by peers (Cundiff & Matthews, 2018). Research by Benenson et al. (2003) discovered that females reported more fragility in their closest same-sex friendships and that their friendships lasted for shorter periods when compared with males.

Peer group relationships and the behaviour of boarders

Studies indicate that benefits of peer affiliations in teenage years include positive outcomes in building future relationships (Cundiff & Matthews, 2018). In this context, peer group memberships provide individuals platforms for learning about the requirements of different peer affiliations (Stanton-Salazar & Spina, 2005).

Similar findings by Hawley, Little & Card (2007) showed that peer groups offer learning opportunities and social support networks that are either negative or positive in nature. Moreover, others found out that peer groups also provide the opportunity for one to observe and learn about the strategies that others implement when solving problems or when handling life situations (Palmonari et al., 1991). Matt and Dean (1993) highlighted that peer groups fulfil significant social support roles that offer social learning opportunities amongst peer members; peer group affiliations offer benefits to an individual's overall physical health as well as their emotional and psychological well-being.

Research by Cundiff & Matthews (2018) suggested that males who are more socially integrated with peers reported lower health issues. The same benefits are extended to females as well, with reported higher peer participation and encouragement being significantly related to higher levels of physical activity (Verloigne et al., 2016). Even so, peer groups are reported to be a source of social stress; in most cases, stress associated with peer groups is related to compromise in the emotional well-being of learners, more especially amongst females (Moran & Eckenrode, 1991). Equally, having strong social support fostered

from peer groups was found to be associated with higher levels of self-esteem and lower levels of depression more predominantly in males than in females (Moran et al., 1991).

Peer group composition and academic performance.

Boarding schools across the globe have well-established institutional norms and values. For instance, researches done by Ryan (2000), shows that peer groups have an important influence on academic achievement, beliefs, and behaviours of peers. Similarly, Parker & Asher (1993) asserted that the ways and manner in which individuals engage with each other in the school context is influenced to a certain extent by their attitudes and the type of peer groups that they voluntarily join or are forced to join.

Ryan (2000) further found out that those students who had high-achieving friends, had greater academic achievement overtime when compared to students who maintained relations with lower achieving friends. Similarly, this research (Ryan, 2000) also suggested that when learners associate with peers who have positive attitudes towards their schoolwork, learners are likely to improve their academic performance. Furthermore, associating with highly motivated peers in boarding schools may act as a protective factor and avoidance of unruly behaviours in the school environment more particularly among male peer groups.

A study by Grulund (1990) indicated that acceptance by a peer group may have positive effect on the child; a child who is not brilliant enough may do better if he is accepted by a group that is inclined to study. It has been observed that a child learns more easily within his peer group. Where he is wrong, he prefers to be corrected by a member of his peer group than by the teacher.

Methodology

This study used the case study approach to evaluate the Impact of Peer Influence on Student Behaviour and Academic Performance in a boarding school. Extensive interview questions were developed using the Social Learning Theory constructs to gather individual's perceptions, experiences and reactions from 11 boarders – 7 girls and 4 boys who voluntarily participated with the consent of their parents. Random sampling was done to select respondents across form 2 to 4 aged between 14 and 18 and have been a boarder for at least two years. The responses were recorded and transcribed for data analysis and presentation.

Data collection, analysis and interpretation

This study used the Thematic Analysis model by Miles, Huberman and Saldana (2014) to answer research questions. Data was encrypted and reduced to workable themes in order to assess the influence of peer pressure on students' behaviour and academic performance. Furthermore, data was coded to identify predominant peer groups' existent in private boarding schools. Respondents perspectives and views were categorised into major themes mainly peer group relationships and the behaviour of boarders, and, peer group composition and academic performance.

The purpose of breaking down data into themes was to determine and evaluate if peer pressure has an impact on boarders behaviour and academic performance. Predominant peer groups were used to determine the level of influence peer pressure exerts on individual students. Peer group relationships and peer group composition were used as significant factors to determine the degree of the impact of peer pressure.

Findings

This study evaluated the impact of peer pressure on students' behaviour and academic performance in a private boarding school. Findings from data analysis revealed 3 major themes as discussed below:

Predominant Peer Groups in Boarding Schools

Findings of this study revealed that in boarding schools, there are two main peer groups, which consists of male peer groups and female peer groups. Participants pointed out that they adjust their opinions, choices and behaviour to conform to those of others in the group. Findings showed that in Boarding schools, males tend to be predominant in behaviour as opposed to female counterparts.

Findings also indicated that females form groups based on their social status, intimacy and support for academic affairs. Female participants affirmed that their interactions are predominantly formed from

pairs to group of friends or cliques who regularly meet and interact with each other. Further, female participants indicated that peer groups influence what they value, whom they talk to and hang around with; their likes and dislikes are mostly influenced by the opinions of peers. In addition, respondents pointed out that, senior students usually adopt juniors or new comers in order to play as role models. Thus, juniors easily fall prey, as they automatically have to fit within the group and follow the stipulated grounding roles.

On the other hand, findings further indicated that male peer groups are formed in order to take dominance of resources and territory, which in most cases leads to divisions and formation of smaller peer groups. Findings revealed that in the males' dormitory, one peer group takes dominance and superiority over other groups; a group character that most often leads to bullying. This peer group dominance and character is quite common with males when compared to females. Male participants of this study highlighted that male peer groups claimed seniority or dominance based on who came first to school, age, or economic background. Thus, findings revealed that peer group influence among males manifested itself through aggressiveness, coercion and outright force.

Effects of Peer Group Relationships on Peer Behavior

Findings also revealed that to some extent, everyone in boarding has some levels of influence to other students either directly or indirectly. It is perceived by all participants that boarders do experience peer influence, either negatively or positively.

Findings revealed that boarders are under a strong influence of peers, which leads to a change of personality and behaviour as they long for acceptance by others, or want to belong with others. Further, findings revealed that both females and males easily give into peer pressure and manifest group behaviour. Participants pointed out that these behaviours impact on them one-way or the other. For females, the influence is so strong because they learn to display socially unacceptable behaviours, for instance, their language and conduct totally changes; female participants asserted that they start 'passing mockery jokes' to their classmates or colleagues as well as despising and forsaking former friends in order to be accepted by their new affiliations.

Participants perceived that the boarding house is a place with high levels of peer influence as all boarders face peer pressure at one point or another. Findings revealed that the degree of attachment and commitment of members to each other and on the group norms play a vital role as this makes them vulnerable. On the male section of the boarding house, findings indicated that the heterogeneity of their population offers them an opportunity to have power over others and this result in aggression and violence. Participants cried of being terrorised by seniors because they are strong, powerful and aggressive. They pointed that this makes them to seek refuge in peer groups for protection purposes only to learn unacceptable behaviour as they interact with each other in the group.

Junior participants affirmed that they are subjected to peer group influence upon arrival into boarding and this result in early engagement in unruly practices like taking drugs, alcohol, tobacco, weapons as well as bullying others who are not part of any group or who are a misfit in the group, and vandalise school property. Participants pointed out that male peer groups deliberately break school rules to show their disapproval of the school authority and to challenge it. Therefore, according to findings, male peer groups are mainly involved in antisocial behaviours.

Contrary to these negative circumstances, some boarders indicated that they were transformed into better persons due to peer influence. In this respect, findings showed that there is also positive peer pressure, which leads to good behaviour modelling as expected in a private boarding school environment.

Peer influence and Learner Academic Performance

Participants' affirmed that peer group influence has both positive and negative effects on their academic performance. Some participants disagreed that their friends perform well academically while others agreed that in their peer groups they encourage each other to work hard in school. One or two participants strongly agreed that their friends affect their academic work positively. All female participants strongly agreed that occasionally the peer groups which they affiliate to makes fun of those who do well academically because they care less about academic excellence.

In addition, all participants strongly agreed that the only time they spend time with their peers to discuss academic work or revise for examinations is towards the end of the term. Female participants

consented that they believe they can do better if everyone in their peer group concentrates on school work throughout, especially if for once they can have 'academically focused' role models.

However, in this study, findings established bullying as one of the predominant behaviours impeding academic performance. Findings also revealed that bullying normally occurs in the absence of supervisors, thereby making it difficult for the administrators to contain it. Because of this bad treatment, which in most cases is done by dominant male peer groups, participants revealed that when a boarder is terrorised they are unable to find the interest to attend school, to the degree that some begin to miss classes, and consequently their academic performance declines. Even worse, participants revealed that most of victimised students withdraw from boarding for the fear of their safety and well-being.

What's more and important from these findings is that participants iterated that there is a positive influence amongst certain peer groups, which leads to peers forming reading, and discussion groups oriented towards academic excellence.

Summary and conclusion

This research discovered that students in boarding schools and within peer groups make decisions from an adaptive perspective, which is influenced by personal belonging, benefits, shared values and beliefs. Findings revealed that peer groups do not allow teenagers to be 'themselves' in the truest sense of the word. In boarding schools, students have to put on an act in order to gain acceptance from their peer group. Furthermore, this research revealed the high value placed on social status by female learners in the boarding environment while males placed their values on dominion over resources and territory.

Findings showed that boys are more likely to engage in overt and physical aggression that leads to bullying and self-assertion. It is also well established that girls are more likely to engage in relational or indirect aggression with their peers when relationships do not work out. Peer influence has been established to have direct influence on the behaviour of learners and academic performance. This study found out that students, who were bullied, were negatively affected either emotionally or academically. Studies by Spadafora et al. (2018) confirmed that witnesses to bullying situations choose to ignore the negative behaviour when they perceived possible personal harm. This is consistent with what participants of this study highlighted.

These findings also indicated that those who are involved in motivated peer groups reported that peer affiliations improved their behaviour and academic performance in a positive manner. Moreover, these findings revealed that a student who is brilliant but is surrounded by dull friends would lose interest in learning. Whereas, a peer group inclined to study would have a positive effect on an academically challenged member and stimulate their interest on learning as asserted by Howard (2004).

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study.

- It is recommended that schools' guidance and counselling departments guide students on the importance of carefully choosing friends so that their attitudes towards learning would be improved as the peer group they belong to can have an effect on their learning either negatively or positively.
- The School Administration must channel peer group energies to promoting good learning behaviour by appointing them as prefects.
- The Pastoral Department in Secondary Schools should take it upon themselves to effectively teach students how to set boundaries with peers.
- Boarding schools in Botswana should improve the supervision of boarding students by implementing and reinforcing school rules and policies for effective management of boarding students.
- Boarding schools should implement and reinforce surveillance cameras in the campus so that bullying indicted could be easily recorded and traced.
- Implement intervention strategies that seek to promote teamwork and good conduct amongst learners.
- Provide academic counseling for students who are victims of peer abuse.

Recommendations for further studies

This study suggests further research in the following areas;

- For adding more knowledge to this study, future research should 'evaluating the adaptive perspective of learners on peer group's dynamics in boarding schools' in order to better understanding the social and personal peer group's dynamics at play in boarding schools and also to use these findings to create effective intervention strategies.

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